

THE EFFECTS OF PARENTAL SOCIO-ECONOMIC BACKGROUND ON ADOLESCENTS' RISKY SEXUAL BEHAVIOURS AND THE COUNSELLING IMPLICATION.

By

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Abstract

Adolescents are fond of engaging in behavioural experimentation which often results in risky sexual behaviours that can expose them to serious health consequences. This study examined the influence of gender and parental socio-economic background on adolescents' risky sexual behaviours. The study adopted a descriptive survey method in which a sample of two hundred and eighty six in-school adolescents drawn from Abeokuta and Sango- Ota, Ogun State was used. The adolescent sexual risk-taking behaviour scale and socio-economic status scale were used in data collection. Two hypotheses were postulated and tested using t-test statistical method at 0.05 level of significance. Findings showed significant difference between male and female adolescents in their risky sexual behaviour while adolescents from low socio economic background demonstrated higher sexual risk taking behaviour than those from high socio-economic background. The study portends certain implications for counselling with a view of fostering healthy lifestyles among adolescents.

Keywords: Adolescents, Risky Sexual Behaviours, Gender, Parental Socio-Economic Background

Problem and Background

The negative consequences of adolescence sexual behaviour have generated a myriad of concerns from all and sundry. Adolescent sexuality is less often studied than sexual intercourse. As a result of this, the wide range

of non-coital sexual activity that adolescents experience is less understood. A wide range of factors influence and are affected by the timing and frequency of adolescents' sexual activity (Kirby, 2001). Neighborhood characteristics, socio-economic status, parent's marital status, sibling characteristics, sexual abuse and biological factors all have been shown to be related to teenage sexual behavior (Miller, Benson and Galbraith, 2001). Living in neighborhoods with low socioeconomic status and high disorder or hazards are associated with higher risk sexual behaviour whereas high neighborhood monitoring and high neighborhood religious practice are associated with lower sexual risk behaviour. (Ramirez-Valles, Zimmerman, and Newcomb 1998; Upchurch, Aneshensel, Sucoff and Levi-Storms, 1998)

According to Taris and Semin (1997); Ramirez-Valles et al. (1998); high socioeconomic status of parents most often has been found to be associated with lower risk of having had intercourse and later sexual debut for adolescents while Miller, Sabo, Farrell, Barnets & Melnick (1998) found no relationship between family income and teenage sexual behavior.

Miller et al. (2001) also reported that in most studies, living in other than a two-parent home (e.g., single parent, step, divorced, or other nontraditional family setting) is associated with increased risk of adolescent sexual intercourse. Also, having sexually active, pregnant, or parenting older siblings was found to be related to younger sibling's more risky sexual behavior (East 1996), although this effect may be mediated by a positive sibling relationship.

Also, parental control and monitoring were generally found to be related to decreased probability of sexual intercourse among teenagers (Miller et al., 2001). Parental rules, monitoring and presence were related to decreased and more responsible sexual activity (Miller et al., 2001; Rodgers 1999). However, a mixed outcome by age, with parental monitoring of adolescents led to decreased sexual activity.

In another study, Rodgers (1999) found parental monitoring to be associated with lower risk sexual behaviour, but parent's psychological control was related to higher risk sexual behaviour. Upchurch et al. (1999) also found that intrusive control by parents was linked to increased sexual behaviour among teenagers.

The relationship between parent/child communication and adolescent sexual activity is less well understood. Although several studies report that frequent and positive parent/child communication about sex is related to less risky adolescent sexual behaviour (East 1996; Miller et al., 2001), others report no relationship and a few even reported a positive association between parent/child communication and riskier sexual behaviour in teenagers (Miller et al., 2001).

Parent's values relating to teenage sexual activity are clearly associated with teenager's reported sexual behaviour. Researches show that teenagers whose parents disapprove of teenage sex are less likely to have intercourse (Jaccard, Dittus, and Gordon 1998; and Miller et al., 2001). Conversely, mothers' permissive attitudes were found to be related to increased adolescent sexual intercourse (Taris and Semin 1997). Parents' attitudes alone are not responsible for this effect, because some studies suggest that adolescents' perception of their parents' attitudes is more important than the parent's actual attitude.

According to UNESCO (2009), the sexual development of a person is a process that comprises physical, psychological, emotional, social and cultural dimensions. It is also inextricably linked to the development of one's gender identity and it unfolds within specific socio-economic and cultural contexts. The transmission of cultural values from one generation to the next forms a critical part of socialization; it includes values related to gender and sexuality. In many communities, young people are exposed to several sources of information and values from parents, teachers, media and peers who often

In many communities, young people are exposed to several sources of information and values from parents, teachers, media and peers who often present them with alternative or even conflicting values about gender and sexuality while in some cases issues relating to sex are hardly discussed with teenagers; parents are often reluctant to engage in discussion of sexual matters with children because of cultural norms, their own ignorance or discomfort.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2003), in many cultures puberty represents a time of social as well as physical change for both boys and girls. For boys, puberty can be a gateway to increased freedom, mobility and social opportunities. For girls, puberty may signal the beginning of adult life, with marriage and childbearing as expected possibilities in the near future.

The patterns of sexual risk taking vary across gender lines among adolescents. It was generally opined that naturally males tend to be bolder and more adventurous than females in most socio-cultural contexts and Uwakwe (2008) reported that in a cultural setting like Nigeria, males more than females are systematically oriented towards valour and adventure which are implicit correlates of risk-taking behaviours.

Much of the interest in adolescent sexual intercourse is driven by several of its serious consequences, including sexually transmitted diseases (STDs), unwanted pregnancy and birth. The rate of sexual intercourse among teenagers varies a great deal between cultures. In the United States for instance, there is considerable variation according to age, socioeconomic status, geographic location and race/ethnicity. Most of these differences can be attributed to a wide range of biological and social factors (Flanigan, 2001), while among Nigerian adolescents, variables like family history, parental education and type of parental care influence risky sexual behaviours. If teens feel parental support, feel a connection to their parents, and are aptly

supervised by them, they are less likely to have early sexual exposure and become pregnant. If parents model sexual risk taking behaviour, such as early child bearing, or permissive attitude towards pre-marital sex, adolescents from such environment could engage in early sexual intercourse. (Abu and Akerele, 2006)

Miller et al. (2001) also contended that family influence on adolescent sexual behaviour can be genetic or biological variables. Hormonal level and the timing of puberty, which can affect sexual behaviour, are partially hereditary. If a mother is young at her first intercourse, it is more likely that both son and daughter will have sex before age 14. Socio-economic status of parents based on indices such as parents' income, religion, type of housing, nature of job, social value, and the environment affect the sexual behaviour of adolescent either positively or negatively; Also, the findings revealed that if an adolescent resides in the "ghettos" or in the slums, there is every tendency for such an adolescent to be prone to early sexual activity and juvenile delinquency than those from well organized residential areas. Uwakwe (2008) further found that adolescent from high socioeconomic background showed higher tendency toward risk-taking behaviours than those from low socio-economic orientation. Aremu (2002) reported that those who come from low strata of socio-economic conditions where accommodation is a single room; where parents cannot fulfill the legitimate needs of their children; where the children do not feel secured and emotionally satisfied tend to be sexually permissive. In the same vein, the World Health Organisation (2003) reported that socio-economic status of parents determines to a large extent, adolescents social behaviour in the society.

From this premise therefore, the present study was designed to investigate the effects of gender and parental socio-economic status on adolescents' risky sexual behaviours and the counselling interventions which could foster healthy sexual lifestyle among Nigerian adolescents.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance;

- (1) There will be no significant difference in the sexual risk taking behavioural patterns of male and female adolescents.
- (2) There will be no significant difference in the sexual risk-taking behavioural patterns of adolescents from high and those from low socio-economic backgrounds.

Methodology

This study is a descriptive survey involving the collection of data on the patterns of sexual risk taking behaviours among adolescents that are prone to the negative consequences of risky sexual behaviour. A total of 286 adolescents from different socioeconomic background were randomly sampled from Abeokuta and Sango Ota in Ogun State, Nigeria. Out of this number, 162 were females while the remaining 124 were males with mean ages of 15.64 and 16.03 respectively.

Instrumentation

The instrument used in this study was the adolescent sexual risk-taking behaviour scale which is an adaptation from the HIV risk-taking behaviour scale developed. The instrument was validated by administering to a sample of 146 adolescents. To establish the reliability of the instrument, the test-retest reliability was used and an index of 0.78 was obtained. Also, the socio economic status scale was used to categorize the study population into high and low socio-economic backgrounds.

Data Analysis

The t-test statistic of independent means was employed in the data analysis.

Results

Hypothesis 1

This hypothesis states that there will be no significant difference in the sexual risk taking behavioural patterns of male and female adolescents. This hypothesis was rejected on the basis of analysis made on the data collected. Thus, a significant difference was observed in the sexual risk-taking behaviours of male and female adolescents in this study. This analysis indicated that males demonstrated more sexual risk taking behaviours than females.

Table 1 T-test comparison of male and female adolescents' sexual risk-taking behaviours

Sex	N	X	S.D	Df	t-cal	Remark
Male	165	98.61	20.37	284	16.57	S
Female	121	62.54'	14.69			

Significant at 0.05

Hypothesis 2

This hypothesis states that there will be no significant difference in the sexual risk taking behavioural patterns of adolescents from high and those from low socio-economic backgrounds. The analysis of data reveals that a significant difference existed in the two groups and as such, the hypothesis was rejected.

Tablet T-test comparison of adolescents socio-economic backgrounds and their sexual risk-taking behaviours

Socio-economic Status	N	X	S.D	Df	t-cal	Remark
Low	154	112.41	26.62	284	5.98	S
High	132	96.57	15.91			

Significant at 0.05

Discussion

The first hypothesis which stated that there will be no significant difference in the sexual risk taking behavioural patterns of male and female adolescents was not accepted. Male adolescents in the study demonstrated higher sexual risk-taking behaviours than their female counterparts ($t=16.57 < 0.05$). This implies that sex of adolescents determine their pattern of sexual risk-taking behaviours. This finding suggests that male adolescents are prone to higher sexual risk-taking behaviours which could expose them to the negative consequences of engaging in such maladaptive behaviours; this lends credence to the view that naturally males tend to be bolder and more adventurous than females in most socio-cultural contexts and Uwakwe (1998) that in a cultural setting like Nigeria, males more than females are systematically oriented towards valour and adventure which are implicit correlates of risk-taking behaviours.

The second hypothesis that there will be no significant difference in the sexual risk-taking behavioural patterns of adolescents from high and those from low socioeconomic backgrounds was also not accepted ($t=5.98 < 0.05$). Adolescents from low socio-economic background demonstrated higher sexual risk taking behavioural pattern than those from high socio-economic background. The plausible reason for this may be due to the fact that in most

Nigerian families, issues relating to sex are not freely discussed with adolescents especially in low socio-economic background families. However parents in the high socio-economic background families encourage their wards to discuss intimate sexual relationship through which they can be appropriately guided. The relationship between parent/child communication and adolescent sexual activity is important; several studies report that frequent and positive parent/child communication about sex is related to less risky adolescent sexual behaviour (East 1996; Miller et al., 2001).

Implications for Counselling

This research has shown the relationship between gender and parental socioeconomic status on adolescents' risky sexual behaviours with adolescents from low socio-economic background showing higher risk-taking behaviour than their counterparts from high socio-economic background. Consequently, there is an urgent need to educate parents from the low strata of the society on how to encourage healthy sexual lifestyle among their children by encouraging them to discuss their intimate relationship with the opposite sex with them so that they can be appropriately guided.

On the other hand, male participants in this study demonstrated higher risk taking behaviour than their female counterparts; this invariably shows need for closer monitoring of male children due to their adventurous nature, males within the Nigerian socio-cultural milieu tend to exude dominance over females and this inadvertently contributes to their tendency to sexually exploit their female friends by regarding sex as a pre-requisite for showing love. Therefore, there is need for Counsellors to put in place effective psychological measures that would discourage male adolescents from taking undue advantage over their female counterparts; this can be done by educating them extensively on how to maintain healthy relationship with the opposite sex without necessarily leading to sex.

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